

Prevalence of Fasciola Species among Cattle Slaughtered in Lafia Modern Abattoir, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Abdullahi M. Musa¹ and David Ehizibolo²

¹Department of Veterinary Services, Nasarawa State Ministry of Agriculture,

²National Veterinary Research Institute, VOM

Received 1 October, 2025, Accepted 15 October, 2025, Published 30 October 2025

Fasciolosis is an economically important parasitic disease of domestic ruminants caused by *Fasciola hepatica* and *Fasciola gigantica*. The infection leads to considerable financial losses through liver condemnation and decreased productivity. This study investigated prevalence of *Fasciola* species among cattle slaughtered at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Over three-month period (June to August 2025), 400 cattle were examined post-mortem for adult flukes and characteristic liver lesions. Of these, 68 (17%) were infected with *Fasciola* species, with *Fasciola gigantica* being the predominant species identified. Infection rates were higher in females (19.2%) than in males (15.1%) and were most prevalent in older cattle (>4 years). The findings demonstrate that fasciolosis remains a major cause of liver condemnation in Lafia abattoir, indicating ongoing exposure of cattle to contaminated pastures and water sources. Regular deworming, improved drainage of grazing areas, and increased farmer awareness are recommended to reduce infection rates.

Keywords: Fasciola, prevalence, cattle, fasciolosis, abattoir, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Fasciolosis is a parasitic disease of significant veterinary and public health concern caused by trematodes of the genus *Fasciola*, primarily *Fasciola hepatica* and *Fasciola gigantica*. In the tropical Africa, *F. gigantica* is dominant specie responsible for most infection in cattle causing economic losses due liver condemnation. *Fasciola* requires intermediate host (*Lymnaea* snail) which thrives better in swampy grazing area.

The disease primarily affects the liver of domestic ruminants such as cattle, sheep, and goats, although humans can also become infected by ingestion vegetable or water contaminated with metacercariae, making it a zoonotic infection. In livestock, fasciolosis cause substantial economic losses due to reduced meat and milk production, decreased fertility, poor weight gain, and condemnation of infected livers during post-mortem inspection. The disease is endemic in many tropical and

subtropical regions where climatic and ecological conditions support the survival of the intermediate snail host (*Lymnaea* species).

In Nigeria, fasciolosis has been documented in various parts of the country, with prevalence rates influenced by ecological and management factors. However, limited information exists on the occurrence of *Fasciola* infection in abattoirs across Nasarawa State. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the prevalence and distribution of *Fasciola* species in cattle slaughtered at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, providing baseline data to support effective control strategies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted at Lafia Modern Abattoir, located in Lafia, the capital city of Nasarawa State,

*Corresponding author's e-mail: bdu2musa@gmail.com

Table 1: Prevalence of *Fasciola* Species in Cattle Slaughtered at Lafia Abattoir

Variable	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
Male	199	30	15.1
Female	201	38	18.9
< 2 years	92	10	10.9
2–4 years	188	31	16.5
> 4 years	120	27	22.5
Total	400	68	17.0

Nigeria. Lafia lies between latitude 8°29'N and longitude 8°32'E, within the Guinea savanna ecological zone. The area experiences two distinct seasons: a wet season (May–October) and a dry season (November–April), with an average annual rainfall of approximately 1,200 mm and a mean temperature of 27°C. Livestock production is a major economic activity in the region. Lafia, Nasarawa state has a lot of swampy areas due to irrigation in dry season farming which make snail thrives well.

Study Design and Sample Size

A cross-sectional study design was employed. A total of 400 cattle slaughtered over a three-month period (June–August 2025) were randomly selected and examined. Data on sex, age, and breed was recorded for each animal. Age of cattle was estimated based on dentition patterns as described by Pace and Wakeman (2003).

Post-Mortem Examination

Routine meat inspection was conducted following the procedures recommended by the Federal Department of Livestock and Pest Control Services (FDLPCS, 1992). Each liver was visually examined and palpated. Suspected livers were incised to detect the presence of adult flukes and associated pathological changes such as fibrosis, thickened bile ducts, and dark brown exudates. Adult flukes were collected and identified morphologically according to description of Soulsby (1982).

Data Analysis

Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square (χ^2) tests to assess associations between infection prevalence and variables such as age and sex. Results were presented in percentages, and statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Of the 400 cattle examined, 68 were found to be infected with *Fasciola* species, representing an overall prevalence of 17.0% (Table 1). Morphological identification showed that *Fasciola gigantica* was the predominant species,

accounting for 89.7% of infections, while *Fasciola hepatica* constituted 10.3%. The prevalence of infection was higher among older cattle (>4 years) compared to younger ones, and females showed a slightly higher rate of infection than males; however, these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

The 17% prevalence of fasciolosis recorded in this study indicates that the disease remains a significant parasitic infection among cattle slaughtered at the Lafia abattoir. The finding is comparable to reports from other parts of northern Nigeria, such as 15.4% in Bauchi and 18.2% in Kaduna (Karshima et al 2016; Isah 2019). Differences in prevalence across regions may be influenced by ecological factors, management practices, and the distribution of intermediate snail hosts.

Predominance of *Fasciola gigantica* observed in this study aligns with previous findings across tropical Africa, where this species is more adapted to warmer climates and aquatic environments (Mas-Coma et al, 2005). The higher infection rate in older cattle could be due to prolonged cumulative exposure to infective metacercariae during grazing (Elelu et al, 2018; Rana et al 2019). Slightly higher prevalence in females may be linked to physiological stress such as pregnancy and lactation, which may lower immunity (Aliyu et al 2014).

Fasciolosis causes considerable economic losses due to liver condemnation, reduced productivity, and decreased market value of affected animals. Beyond economic impact, the disease also poses a zoonotic risk to humans through consumption of raw or undercooked aquatic vegetation and contaminated water. Effective control measures, including regular deworming, proper grazing management, and snail control are therefore essential to reduce the burden of the disease.

CONCLUSION

This study established that fasciolosis is prevalent among cattle slaughtered at Lafia Modern Abattoir, with *Fasciola gigantica* as the predominant species. The disease continues to contribute to significant economic losses

through liver condemnation and reduced animal productivity. Control efforts should prioritize improved farm management, regular veterinary inspection, and public awareness among livestock handlers to minimize both economic and public health risks.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Routine meat inspection and proper condemnation of infected livers should be enforced.
2. Livestock farmers should be educated on regular deworming and safe grazing practices.
3. Environmental management such as drainage of stagnant water to limit snail habitats should be promoted.
4. Further epidemiological studies incorporating snail intermediate hosts and seasonal variations are recommended.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, M. I., Bello, A., & Yusuf, M. (2010). Prevalence of fascioliasis in cattle slaughtered at Bauchi abattoir, Nigeria. *Nigerian Veterinary Journal*, 31(3), 230–234.
- Aliyu, A. A., Jajere, S. M., & Lawal, A. I. (2012). Studies on fasciolosis in cattle slaughtered at Kaduna abattoir. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*, 33(1), 89–93.
- Aliyu AA, Ajogi AI, Ajanusi OJ, & Reuben RC (2014). Epidemiological studies of *Fasciola gigantica* in cattle in cattle, Nigeria using coprology and serology. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology*; 6 (2) 85-91
- Anosike, J. C., Nwoke, B. E. B., & Njoku, A. J. (2001). Epidemiology of fascioliasis among domestic animals in Imo State, Nigeria. *Animal Research International*, 2(1), 33–37.
- Elelu N, Eisler MC (2018): A review of bovine fasciolosis and other trematodes in Nigeria. *Journal of Helminthology*, 92(2),128-141.
- Isah UM. Studies on the prevalence of fasciolosis among ruminant animals in northern Bauchi state, north eastern Nigeria. *Parasite Epidemiology and Control*. 2019;5:e00090
- FDLPCS (1992). *Meat Inspection Manual*. Federal Department of Livestock and Pest Control Services, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Karshima NS, Bata SI, Bobbo AA (2016): Prevalence, risk factors and economic losses associated with fasciolosis in slaughtered cattle in Bauchi, North Eastern Nigeria. *Alexandria Journal of Vet Sc.* 2016; 50 (1):87-93
- Mas-Coma, S., Esteban, J. G., & Bargues, M. D. (2005). Epidemiology of human fascioliasis: a review and proposed new classification. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 83(6), 540–546.
- Mas-Coma S, Bargues MD, Valero MA (2005): *Fasciola* & other plant borne trematodes zoonoses. *Int J Parasitol.* 2005;35(11-12):1255-1278
- Nwosu, C. O., Anene, B. M., & Ogunrinade, A. F. (2007). Studies on the prevalence of bovine fascioliasis and economic losses due to liver condemnation in some abattoirs in eastern Nigeria. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 39(4), 291–294.
- Pace, J. E., & Wakeman, D. L. (2003). Determining the age of cattle by their teeth. University of Florida Cooperative Extension Service Fact Sheet CIR253.
- Pfukenyi, D. M., Mukaratirwa, S., Willingham, A. L., & Monrad, J. (2006). Epidemiology and control of fasciolosis in cattle and sheep in Zimbabwe: a review. *Journal of the South African Veterinary Association*, 77(1), 2–8.
- Phiri, A. M., Phiri, I. K., & Sikasunge, C. S. (2005). Seasonal pattern of bovine fasciolosis in Zambia. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 134(1–2), 87–92.
- Soulsby, E. J. L. (1982). *Helminths, Arthropods and Protozoa of Domesticated Animals*. 7th ed. Baillière Tindall, London.
- Rana MAA, Roohi N, Khan MA (2019). Fascioliasis in cattle: A review. *The Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences*. 24(3)
- Urquhart, G. M., Armour, J., Duncan, J. L., Dunn, A. M., & Jennings, F. W. (2000). *Veterinary Parasitology*. 2nd ed. Blackwell Science, Oxford.